

DESIGN A ROLE PLAYING GAMES AS LEARNING MEDIA

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Abstract

A digital game with a Role-Playing Game (RPG) type is one of the games that has a storyline that has been set in a scenario. What makes this game exclusive is that there are scenarios and challenges to complete. We created a Game-Based Learning combined with challenges in RPG games that must be completed with the aim of learning using Quest-Driven Learning (QDL). QDL is a challenge-based learning model in digital games with the aim of instilling the desired learning value in the game journey process. In the process of making digital games, of course, an attractive manufacturing model is needed so that it uses Game Content Model (GCM) rules in the stage of making this game. GCM is a games creation formality with the required standards and entangles the needs of game players with digital game makers. In our study using this model, it was found that 88% of players categorized it as a learning game and 92% said it was fun to play and learn.

Keywords: RPG, QDL, GCM

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the game is a very promising industry phenomenon, according to a survey conducted in the United States as much as 58% of the community is a game player from a young to mature age, make of 20.77 billion dollars profit in the gaming industry in the United States in 2012 self, where the largest percentage of the type of game being played is a Role playing games (RPG) for 28% of all games console base [ESA, (2013)]. Video games have enormous potential as training instruments for cognitive intelligence over standardized testing, with their natural motive power, and have shown benefits for a very wide range of aspects of cognition [Schmück et al, (2019)].

Currently learning with games is still not recognized by the formal education system [Ramic-Brkic, B., (2019)] but can be an alternative to learning outside the formal environment. Object of this research is to build a gaming system with games technology disciplines, rules Role Playing Games in the learning process. Role Playing Games world which a person goes into a role in the game world then given the opportunity to participate and interact with the objects of the world [Hitchens et al., (2007)], where there are scenarios and challenges, Moral values and learning targets will be implemented using Quest-Driven Learning Model (QDL). Quest-Driven Learning is a learning method on the game that aims to mix is a challenge-based learning model in digital games with the aim of instilling the desired learning value in the game journey process [Chen et al., (2010)]. Game uses the rules of Game Content Model (GCM) in a stage of development.

Game Content Model (GCM) rules in the stage of making this game. GCM is a games creation formality with the required standards and entangles the needs of game players with digital game makers for serious game model [Tang et al., (2010)]. Serious games can provide increased interest for applications in the delivery of virtual learning heritage, and many examples are well documented in the literature [Hanes et al, (2017)]. This research aims to design systems based RPG of type on Game-Based Learning using Quest-Driven Learning Model for learning system. Development of Game-Based Learning (GBL) the rules of GCM, learning system in the Role-playing mechanism.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

2.1 Objective

The System Development Life Cycle (SDLC) as the method in game sytem development on this research. SDLC is a process aims to provide a structured flow to help produce high-quality software and fulfill the user expectations. Model the software life cycle compare its performance [Saravanan et al., (2020)], the most important part of an SDLC is the quality assurance part or testing phase [Sinha et al., (2021)] with the game type of Role playing games (RPG) combine with formality of Game Content Model (GCM). GCM selectively has been combined with research on game design [Tang et al., (2011)], in order to using concepts that needed for development on GBL formality. The key concept of interrelated representing the rules, playing computer games and information aesthetics and structure of the game, the presentation of games, simulation games, game rules, game scenarios, game shows, goal games, game objects, archives player and the theme of the game [Tang et al., (2011)]. Game Content Model is one component of the Model-Driven serious gaming models. GCM component depicted on Figure 1 below.

Fig 1: Game Content Model (GCM) Components

The research to combine GCM with QDL model. The purpose of the Quest-driven learning model of learning task intended to mix with the search game. In general, quests in the game involve the Non Playable Character (NPC), scripts, tasks, and reward on figure 2[Chen et al., (2010)].

Fig 2: Quest-Driven Learning Model

From Figure 2 above players have a level of interaction to the game world in which there are quests that become the foundation of the learning process. Triggers of quest come from NPC contained within the game world and the NPC will give out awards as a sign quest has been successfully implemented. Learning task in the game triggered by the NPC which is located somewhere in the gaming storylines. Through texts, players needed to find out how to helping the other character by completing the tasks given on the game scenario, such as doing a search, adventure, driving correctly or practice. Result, players can get something worthwhile as a gift for the successful the task compleion of the game story. Broadly speaking, the quest on Role-Playing mechanism refers to the approach QDL Model [Chen et al., (2010)] which apply the concept in the form of reward for the learning process.

2.2 Object of Study

In this study, Role Playing Games used to be the basis of the scheme and the game's storyline. The story itself has been set up to follow the stages of passage level. Players can develop a character in the story.

Construction of many quests including a mini-game, one of them is the quest of learning about the knowledge. The value of the interest comes from the level of rewards to be gained and assist in the resolution and support for the character's abilities.

This study aims to aid the process of learning through the media game to make players understand the concept with different viewpoints, especially in terms of Role Playing Games. Key point and system architecture depicted, as is seemingly in Figure 3 below.

Fig 3: Game Development Concept

This study aims to aid the learning process using the concept of role-playing mechanism. Where implementation of the game world is connected with the scenarios that have been prepared seen from Table 1 below.

Table 1: Game based learning topic implementation

Number	Topic	Implementation
1.	Learning Process	- Storylines
		- Learning Task
		- Mini Games
		- Word of Wisdom
2.	Social Interact	- Interaction with NPC
		- Economic
		- Quest
3.	Self Discipline	- Ordinary work (Sleep, eat, take a bath, trade, etc)

2.3 Implementation

Validation process is the confirmation by examination and provision on development formality that the particular requirements for a special purpose have been fulfilled. Game Content Model (GCM) is a model-based game development contains interactive point that 10 keys in game development:

- (1) Game Structure: where architecture games Role-Playing Games with a world that has wide coverage and have an adventure-quest Quest that must be completed. One quest to be solved have relevance to the understanding the task.
- (2) Game Presentation: the use of the manuscript text, graphics, sound and interactive video. As well as the implementation of Button, list boxes, radio buttons and menus.
- (3) Game Simulation: With 2D display in Real-time with the concept of RPG and Minimal screen display of 1024 x 800 pixels.
- (4) Game Rules: Rule by reward and the turnaround time focused character development, interaction with Non Playable Character (NPC) and the completion of the quest therein.

- (5) Game Scenario: the creation of an area filled with NPCs where characters can connect, engage in economic activities of buying and selling, and get an explanation of the question. Use character images being played. Increase the level of difficulty depending on the stage of the game and increased at each level
- (6) Event Game: implementation of mini games with different challenges with rewards in the form of gifts that can be used to help the game. Begins with the story to support the mini game.
- (7) Game Objectives: designing an adventure game system and learning traffic signs. Condition goal is to finish the game assisted by the rewards that come from questions about traffic signs and some mini-games.
- (8) Game Object: object attributes that character has a level that is affected by the value of Experience and had a very close relationship with the basic elements that affect Health Power, Magic Power, and the basic values of attributes are Strength, Intelligence, Agility, Attack, Defence. There is also a currency values therein. Implementation of pictorial characters with the main character is iconic and has a two-dimensional display. And development capabilities NPC using path finding algorithm A * [Yan et al., (2012)] as the position of the player. Position players used as a reference in the decision used in path finding using the A *.
- (9) Game Player: use of inventory for the storage of goods by the character. Mouse, keyboard and stick. As well as the implementation of the save point to control the game.
- (10) Game Theme: Art style on the implementation of graphics, text, and sound. Seen from Figure 4 Below.

Fig 4: Integration Method Model

3. RESULT

Creating Game-based learning here has opening of the application is index or main page as stated the figure 5. In the index page, there are three menus, namely New Game, Continue, and Options.

Fig 5: Main Page Display

3.1 Learning Events

In this event, the player will be shown learning event on Quest-Driven Learning model. The event is about short explanation of learning quest. The player should learn and memorate all of the terms there to finish that event, as captured in Figure 6 as follows.

Fig 6. Learning Quest On The Game Event

The figure 6 is the picture of NPC about the Learning Quest on the Game Event which all of statements should be learned well in order to finish the event. In this event, the player will be shown the questions related the other learning task. The player should answer the question correctly to finish the event, if the answer is wrong, the player will repeat the game from the beginning as captured in Figure 7 as follows.

Fig 7: The Other Learning Quest

Figure 7 is the picture of NPC about the other quest event which all of statements should be learned well in order to finish the event. In the next event, the player will be shown various NPC which give learning or word of wisdom spread over the game. Some examples of NPC are captured in Figure 8 as follows.

Fig 8. Support NPC Display

4. ANALYSIS

Analysis is one of the important factors in a study, in the analysis we use to find out the impact of game making on players. The point of view used is the effectiveness of the game on learning and the formality of the game's features. Assessment of each respondent assumptions which cannot be disputed. Graph the results of an assessment of the game from each respondent assumptions shown in Figure 9 below.

Fig 9: a. b. c. – Taken from 50 game player samples in range 9 year – 15 year old active playing games.

From the graph in Figure 9 a. for question has a variety of responses; it may be the result of respondents has a different understanding of the genre, the game and also a different experience. Question in Figure 9. b. with answers 88% stated that the game is a learning game. Question in Figure 9. c. Answer 92% said respondents were happy to learn by playing a game of it can be interpreted game. Hal can be interpreted very effective learning games for learning. Questions related to the issue that has a level of true or false value. The question is a question description then sought an equivalent level of understanding of respondents responses.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The Game Content Model (GCM) concept with Role-Playing mechanism have been successful implemented in compliance with 10 own criteria's. Implementation of learning combined with the search process Game-based Learning Quest driven (QDL) can provide a different and fun learning experience with 88% of players categorized it as a learning game and 92% said it was fun to play and learn.

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